

ENOL CONTENT OF 2-FORMYL KETONES.
(HYDROXYMETHYLENE KETONES)

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The enol content of some hydroxymethylene ketones has been determined

Formylation of ketone (I) gives the formyl derivative (II) which according to Claisen (*Ber.*, 1887, 40, 2191) exists mostly in the enolic form (III) and is therefore known as hydroxymethylene ketone.

The actual determination of the enol content in the aldehyde-enol equilibrium mixture (II $\rightleftharpoons$ III) is the object of the present work.

We employed for this purpose the method of Meyer (*Ber.*, 1911, 44, 2718; 1912, 45, 2843) of bromine titration which has been employed in the estimation of enol in keto-enol equilibrium mixture. Addition of bromine to the enol (III), followed by loss of hydrobromic acid, produces the bromo-aldehyde (IV). On adding potassium iodide the hydriodic acid formed reduces (IV) liberating two atoms of iodine per molecule of enol. The iodine is then estimated.

To check the correctness of the results obtained by this method we used another method due to Hibber (*Ber.*, 1921, 54, 902) the principle of which is the estimation of copper in the chloroform-soluble chelate copper salt (V) which the enol forms on addition of

copper acetate. From this solution, on acidifying with sulphuric acid, copper sulphate separates which is estimated iodometrically. One half atom of copper corresponds to one molecule of enol.

As will be seen from the experimental part, the two methods gave concordant results only in two cases. Generally, however, the results of enol estimation by Meyer's method are much higher than those obtained by Hibber's method. It appears that bromine used in the first method affects the equilibrium in aldehyde-enol system. A critical study of the disturbing effect of bromine in bromocarbonyl compounds in general will be the subject of the next communication.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Meyer's Method.—The conditions laid down by the author were strictly adhered to. To the solution of hydroxymethylene ketone in absolute alcohol, kept at -10° , was added alcoholic $N/5$ -bromine in slight excess, the excess being removed by adding alcoholic 10% solution of β -naphthol until the pale yellow colour due to excess of bromine just disappeared. The whole operation was completed within 15 seconds and at -10° . Potassium iodide was then added, the mixture was warmed and the liberated iodine titrated against $N/10$ -sodium thiosulphate.

Hibber's Method.—The author's experimental conditions were followed. A weighed quantity of the hydroxymethylene ketone was dissolved in 30 c.c. of absolute alcohol and the solution was cooled to -10° . To this was added a mixture, kept at -10° , of absolute alcohol (12 c.c.), chloroform (8 c.c.) and aqueous copper acetate (10 c.c. containing 0.0015 g. copper per c.c.). The whole was well stirred and poured into a separating funnel containing 250 c.c. of water at 0° . The whole operation was finished within 15 seconds. The layer of chloroformic copper-enol solution separating was transferred to another separating funnel; the contents of the first funnel were once more extracted with chloroform, the chloroform extracts were mixed, washed with water and decomposed by dilute sulphuric acid. Copper in the aqueous layer of copper sulphate which separated was estimated iodometrically. The percentages of enols obtained by these two methods are shown in the following table.

TABLE I

Hydroxymethylene ketones.	Formula.	Percentage of enol by		Reference.
		Meyer's method.	Hibber's method.	
1. Hydroxymethylene methyl ethyl ketone	$\text{Me}-\text{CO}-\underset{\text{ }}{\text{C}}-\text{Me}$ CHOH	96.1	64.1	Joshi, Kaushal and Deshapande (<i>this Journal</i> , 1941, 18, 479).
2. Hydroxymethylene diethyl ketone	$\text{Et}-\text{CO}-\underset{\text{ }}{\text{C}}-\text{Me}$ CHOH	57.0	35.5	Claisen and Meyerowitz (<i>Ber.</i> , 1889, 22, 3275).
3. Hydroxymethylene cyclohexanone		72.5	74.5	Wallach and Steindorff (<i>Annalen</i> , 1903, 329, 117).
4. Hydromethylene desoxybenzoin	$\text{Ph}-\text{CO}-\underset{\text{ }}{\text{C}}-\text{Ph}$ CHOH	90.2	89.7	Wislicenus and Ruthing (<i>Annalen</i> , 1911, 379, 238)
5. Bromohydroxymethylene acetophenone	$\text{Ph}-\text{CO}-\underset{\text{ }}{\text{C}}-\text{Br}$ CHOH	68.0	34.0	Agarwal, Gupta and Deshapande (<i>this Journal</i> , 1949, 28, 55).

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